

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Slurry Concentrator

Nutrient concentration as a viable technology for slurry management

Challenge

In regions with high livestock density, there is an imbalance between the volume of nutrients generated and the farmland available for their application. While nutrients are essential for crop production, they are also the cause of serious soil, water and atmospheric pollution problems if not properly managed and applied to land.

Aims

To separate manure into two phases: a semi-liquid phase concentrating the majority of the organic matter and nutrients, and a liquid phase with a low nutrient concentration.

Results

- Dilution rates vary (73-88% for breeding farm slurry, 17% for fattening slurry), with breeding farm slurry having 18% volume concentration, 32% total nitrogen, and 77% total phosphorus.
- Low energy usage, with the least favorable tests achieving 0.27 kWh m³ (costing €0.0351 m³).
- Joint analysis confirms concentrator's technological and economic viability.

CONCENTRATED FRACTION

~25% volume

Contains most of the organic fraction, nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus) and larger particles

DILUTED FRACTION

~75% volume

Contains low nutrient concentration

View of the concentrator

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our journey!

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